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AN APPRAISAL OF THE CONVENTION ON THE ELIMINATION OF ALL FORMS OF DISCRIMINATION AGAINST WOMEN (CEDAW) FROM AN ISLAMIC LAW PERSPECTIVE

Muhammad Bashir Alkali, PhD. *

Abstract

Women constitute more than half of the world's population yet categorized as one of the vulnerable groups. Protection of women therefore means protection of a greater part of the human race. The Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) was adopted by the United Nations in order to provide special protection for women against discrimination and all forms of abuse. The Convention is categorized as one of the UN Conventions that has enjoyed the highest ratification in UN history. Islamic law has equally provided protection for women against discrimination and all forms of abuse. Islam came at a time when women were regarded as chattels in most parts of the world. Consequently, Islamic law placed them on the same footing with men, gave them the right to own property and prohibited all forms of discrimination against them. Clearly, both regimes aim to protect women, however certain areas of disagreement have forced several Muslim nations to tender reservation on some articles of the Convention. Reconciliation of these conflicts will no doubt add to the level of protection to be enjoyed by women. This paper therefore intends to examine the Convention, look at its areas of

similarities and differences with Islamic law and suggests ways to reconcile the differences. A doctrinal methodology was adopted in arriving at the findings of this paper.

KEYWORDS: *CEDAW, Islamic Law, Discrimination, Protection, Conflict*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The Nations of the world appreciated the growing rate of discrimination against women and in a move to address this challenge often came up with the grand idea of having a Convention to address discrimination against women. The Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination against Women is one of the United Nations Conventions that has enjoyed the highest ratification.¹ The General Assembly of the United Nations adopted the Convention on 18th December, 1979 and came into force on 3rd September, 1981.² The Convention contains 30 articles with a preamble that lays a proper foundation for the Convention. Islamic law on the other hand provided for the protection of women over 1400 years ago. It dedicated a whole chapter Surah Nisa' for women and placed women on the same footing with men. This paper intends to examine the areas of similarities and differences and equally look into how these differences can be reconciled for the overall good of the women folk. A background on CEDAW and the protection it provides have been discussed in the paper, similarly, signatories, to CEDAW, Islamic law on protection of women etc. have been discussed in the paper. Doctrinal methodology was adopted in this paper.

2.0 THE CONVENTION ON THE ELIMINATION OF ALL FORMS OF DISCRIMINATION AGAINST WOMEN (CEDAW) AND THE PROTECTION IT PROVIDES

2.1 AN OVERVIEW OF CEDAW

The preamble to the Convention acknowledges the great contribution of women to the welfare of the family and society. It states that discrimination against women violates the principles of equality of rights and respect for human dignity, it is an obstacle to the participation of women, on equal terms with men, in the political, social, economic and cultural life of their countries, it hampers the growth of the prosperity of society and the family and makes more difficult the full development of the potentialities of women in the service of their countries and of humanity.³

¹Riggin, J., The Potential Impact of CEDAW Ratification on U.S. Employment Discrimination Law: Lessons from Canada, (2011), vol. 41, Columbia Human Rights Law Review, at 542.

²This is in accordance with Article 27(1) of the Convention which states that the Convention shall enter into force on the thirtieth day after the date of deposit with the Secretary-General of the United Nations of the twentieth instrument of ratification or accession.

³Preamble to CEDAW

The convention started by defining discrimination as thus:

“For the purposes of the present Convention, the term “discrimination against women” shall mean any distinction, exclusion or restriction made on the basis of sex which has the effect or purpose of impairing or nullifying the recognition, enjoyment or exercise by women, irrespective of their marital status, on a basis of equality of men and women, of human rights and fundamental freedoms in the political, economic, social, cultural, civil or any other field.”⁴

The Convention’s principal aim is to remove all forms of discrimination against women in all respect and place women on the same footing with men in the social, political,⁵ cultural and economic spares.⁶ Maternity and child upbringing is a matter of great importance for the survival of the family institution, to this extent, the Convention requires that both parents have equal rights with respect to maternity and their child’s training. The interest of the child must always be put into consideration in all matters relating to the child.⁷ With respect to nationality of children, the Convention requires that both parents must be given the same rights with respect to the nationality of their children.⁸

Trafficking in women is a matter of concern in most parts of the world. Women are often trafficked for prostitution and other dirty businesses. The Convention requires State Parties to take appropriate measures to ensure that trafficking in women, prostitution and all forms of exploitation of the women folk is prohibited.⁹ The Convention opposes any situation that will automatically change the nationality of women due to marriage or render her stateless.¹⁰ In appreciation of the fact that education is a very important instrument for development, the Convention requires State Parties to give equal opportunities for both men and women without discrimination.¹¹ Discrimination in education includes sports and

⁴ Article 1

⁵ Article 7 requires states parties to ensure equal rights are provided for men and women with respect to election matters.

⁶ Article 4

⁷ Article 5(b); see also 16(1)(d)

⁸ Article 9(2)

⁹ Article 6

¹⁰ Article 9(1)

¹¹ Article 10

vocational education.¹² Just like education, the Convention has equally guaranteed the right of every woman to employment.¹³

Discrimination against women in employment matters is an outright contradiction of the spirit of CEDAW. Free choice of employment, equal remuneration and safety in employment must be provided for women without discrimination of any kind.¹⁴ Marriage or maternity must never be a source of discrimination against women.¹⁵ A woman must never be dismissed from work on grounds of marriage or pregnancy and is entitled to maternity leave with pay or with comparable social benefits without loss of former employment, seniority or social allowances.¹⁶

In matters relating to health, pregnancy and maternity, the Convention requires all appropriate measures to be taken by State Parties to ensure that no discrimination is made to women.¹⁷ Adequate nutrition during pregnancy and lactation must be provided for women.¹⁸ In view of the serious challenges faced by rural women, the Convention states that rural women shall be given adequate health care, social security and must be allowed to participate in community activities. With respect to legal matters, women shall be given equal treatment together with men.¹⁹

In civil matters, the Convention requires that women must be given a legal capacity equal to that of men. Right to enter into a contract, ownership of property and the freedom to choose their residence and domicile is provided for women by CEDAW.²⁰ On matters related to marriage, choice of spouse and parenthood, the Convention requires the respect for the rights of women.²¹ The convention categorically states that the betrothal and marriage of a child shall be void and states need to specify the minimum age for marriage in addition to making of compulsory marriage illegal.²²

¹² Article 10(g)

¹³ Article 11(a)

¹⁴ Article 11(1)(b)(d)(f)

¹⁵ Article 11(2)(a)

¹⁶ Article 11(2)(b)

¹⁷ Article 12(1)

¹⁸ Article 12(2)

¹⁹ Article 15(1)

²⁰ Article 15 (2)(3) and (4).

²¹ Article 16(1)

²² Article 16(2)

The Convention provided for the establishment of a committee for the elimination of discrimination against women.²³ The committee meets for a period of less than two weeks annually.²⁴ The formal venue for the Committees meeting is at the United Nations Headquarters in New York.²⁵ In case of argument between States regarding the interpretation of the provisions of the Convention, the first option shall be negotiation, if that fails then arbitration shall be used and where that did not settle the dispute; the International Court of Justice shall be requested to intervene.²⁶

2.2 STATE PARTIES TO CEDAW

As at Saturday 13th November, 2014, there are 188 Parties to the Convention and 99 State Parties have signed and agreed to be bound by the provisions of the Convention.²⁷ Though many States have signed the Convention, most of them have tendered reservations on some provisions of the Convention. The implication of such reservation is that they will not be bound by that particular section for which a reservation is tendered.

According to the Vienna Convention, where a State tenders reservation on any provision of an international instrument, the implication of the reservation is that it is not obliged to observe that provision to which it has tendered a reservation.²⁸ However, the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties states further that a state may not formulate a reservation "incompatible with the object and purpose of the treaty."²⁹ By this provision, though State Parties have the power to tender reservation on the provision of CEDAW, such reservation must not be such as to defeat the object and purpose of the treaty. Interestingly, though CEDAW is one of the UN Conventions with the highest ratification, it is equally the UN Convention that has the highest reservation.³⁰

²³ Article 17

²⁴ Article 20(1)

²⁵ Article 20(2)

²⁶ Article 29(1)

²⁷ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/treaty-bodies/cedaw/cedaw-your-daily-life> viewed on 19th August, 2023.

²⁸ Article 2(1)(d) of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties.

²⁹ Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties Article 19(c)

³⁰ Beate, H., Introduction to CEDAW, Paper presented at the International Training Seminar for NGOs and women's rights activists 13-15 March, 2003, Berlin, Germany.

2.3 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF CEDAW

CEDAW as the sole international legal instrument that aims to fight all forms of discrimination against women principally intends to ensure that women are protected from all forms of discrimination and abuse.³¹ The Convention aims to ensure that women do not suffer any form of discrimination both in public and private spheres.³² CEDAW is such a unique international instrument that aims to foreclose all acts that could possibly lead to discrimination of women. This approach is informed by the fact that discrimination leads to abuse and suffering of women.

The convention requires State Parties to take practical steps in ensuring that the spirit of the Convention is reflected in all its affairs. Women must be allowed to partake in governance and leadership. In appreciation of the peculiar natural health condition of women, the Convention has therefore requested that even in terms of employment, State Parties must ensure pregnancy, child birth etc. are not used to the disadvantage of women. Maternity leave should be a right of women while employers do not deny any such entitlements for women do to such health conditions.

2.4 OPTIONAL PROTOCOLS TO CEDAW

The United Nations General Assembly on the 6th of October, 1999 adopted a 21 Article Optional Protocol to CEDAW. The adoption of the Optional Protocol is a monumental achievement of the UN which aims to re-enforce its commitment towards the protection of women. The Optional Protocol called on all State Parties to the Convention to become party to the new instrument without much delay.³³ The Optional Protocol to CEDAW entered into force on 22 December 2000, following the ratification of the tenth State party to the Convention as required by the Protocol.³⁴ The entry into force of the Optional Protocol puts it on an equal footing with other International instruments with communication procedures like the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the Convention on

³¹Dairiam, S., Using CEDAW to Address Trafficking in Women, in *Gender and Human Rights in the Common Wealth*, edited by Dairiam, S., (London: Common Wealth Secretariat, 2004), at 169.

³²Ibid

³³UN, available at <http://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/protocol/> viewed on 7 November, 2022.

³⁴Article 16 to the Optional Protocol.

the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination, and the Convention against Torture and other Forms of Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment.³⁵

The implication of rarifying the Optional Protocol is that the State Party recognises the competence of the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women to receive and consider complaints from individuals or groups within its jurisdiction. The Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women is the body established by the Optional Protocol to monitor State Parties' compliance with the Convention.³⁶

The Optional Protocol to CEDAW provided for two important communication procedures thus:

Firstly, the first communication procedure allows women either individually or in group to submit to the committee a claim of violation of a right guaranteed under CEDAW. It is important to mention that before any such complain is entertained by the Committee, domestic remedies must have been exhausted and certain procedures must have been complied with.³⁷

However, on receipt of a complaint, the Committee is faced with two levels of inquiry. These relate to the admissibility of the claim after satisfying the requirements set by the protocol as precondition for the admissibility of the facts and the merits of the claim, or whether the facts alleged are considered to constitute a violation of the CEDAW. The claim must be accompanied by all documents which are relevant to both levels of inquiry.

Similarly, details of any administrative or judicial decisions taken at the national level with respect to the matter, including copies of such decisions, as well as copies of all relevant national laws must be made available to the Committee. If the complaint contains sufficient information relating to the admissibility criteria, as well as the merits of the case, the complaint will be 'registered' by the CEDAW Committee, and the procedure for consideration of communications outlined in the Optional Protocol and amplified by the Committee's rules of procedure will begin. It is crucial to fulfill the formal requirements

³⁵Connors J., Introduction to the Optional Protocol and its mechanisms, Paper presented at the International Training Seminar for NGOs and women's rights activists 13-15 March, 2003, Berlin, Germany.

³⁶Ibid

³⁷Such complaints need to be in writing but not through email and not anonymous. See Article 3 of the Protocol.

governing the admissibility of a complaint in order to access the communications procedure.³⁸

Secondly, the Committee is empowered by the Protocol to initiate an inquiry into situations of grave or systematic violations of women's rights.³⁹ This procedure is different from the first one. Under this procedure, there is no need for any formal complaint by any woman or group of women on violation of their rights. Rather, the Committee can suo moto (on its own) start the process of inquiry so long as there is indication of any violation of women's right. Under both situations, for the Committee to have the power of receiving or initiating an investigation, States must be party to the Convention and the Protocol.

Further, upon completion of the inquiry, the Committee is required to transmit its findings to the State party, together with any comments or recommendations. The State has six months to react, and the CEDAW Committee is entitled to request the State party to provide further details of any measures taken in response to the inquiry, including in its next periodic report.⁴⁰ The Protocol includes an "opt-out clause", allowing States upon ratification or accession to declare that they do not accept the inquiry procedure.⁴¹

A very fundamental question or issue for address as far as the Committee is concerned is whether an alleged violation meets the threshold requirement of a grave or systematic violation of the rights under the Convention. Several interpretative statements made by governments on the adoption of the Optional Protocol at the forty-third session of the Commission on the Status of Women raised this issue. For example Egypt expressed the view that the reference to grave violations, using the plural form, means the repeated occurrence of such violations, while Israel expressed its view that the phrase, grave or systematic excluded inquiries into singular, isolated incidents.⁴²

The Optional Protocol to CEDAW is a very important supportive document towards making the respect of rights guaranteed to women by CEDAW practical. This is by ensuring that the violations of rights guaranteed by CEDAW are addressed in a realistic and practical form.

³⁸ Connors J., n. 35.

³⁹ Article 8 and 9 of the Optional Protocol

⁴⁰ Article 18 of the Convention

⁴¹ Article 10 CEDAW

⁴² Beate, H., n. 30, at 21.

A Committee established under the Protocol receives complaints of violation of women's right and can also conduct independent inquiry into any grave systematic violation of women's right.

3.0 PROTECTION OF WOMEN UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

Islam protects women and made adequate provision for their right. Before the advent of Islam most part of the world consider women as property that can be inherited. Islam prohibited this practice and asserted rights and protection for women. The Qur'an states "...And women have rights similar to the rights against them"⁴³ The Prophet (PBUH) stated that the best of you is the best of you to his family and I am the best of you to my family.⁴⁴ Islamic law prohibits all forms of abuse of women such as killing, discrimination and harm.

4.0 PROVISIONS OF CEDAW THAT ARE IN LINE WITH ISLAMIC LAW

A cursory look at CEDAW reveals that it mainly intends to stop discrimination against women. This no doubt has a lot of backing from the Qur'an and other sources of Islamic law. The protection of the right of women is equally an aspect which CEDAW aims to protect.⁴⁵ Under Islamic law, women are guaranteed rights which must be protected and any person that abuses such right stands to face the full wrath of the law.

The Qur'an states that:

*"And they (women) have rights equal to the right against them in an equitable manner"*⁴⁶

This verse has clearly shown that under the shari'a the rights of women is equal to that of men and must be respected by all.⁴⁷ Qur'an used the word "*mithl*" which means "equal to" the implication of the use of this word is that whenever any claim of right is made by a man against the woman, the Qur'an has equally placed a similar responsibility on the men to ensure that they give to the women rights that are equal to that which they demand.⁴⁸

⁴³ Qur'an 2:272

⁴⁴ Sunan al-Tirmidhi 3895

⁴⁵ Nora Abdul Hak, "Women's Rights and the Impact of CEDAW", in Human Rights Law: International, Malaysian and Islamic Perspectives, edited by Sein, A.G., (Malaysia: Sweet and Maxwell Asia, 2012), at 190.

⁴⁶ Qur'an, *al-Baqarah*:282

⁴⁷ Abdullah ibn Abdul Muhsin al-Tarky et al, Tafseer al-Muyassir, (KSA, Mushaf al-Madinah, 2003), 241\

⁴⁸ Ibid

It is important to state that the rights provided under CEDAW came on board less than 50 years ago.⁴⁹ However, the rights provided for women in Islam has been in existence for over 1400 years.⁵⁰ It is interesting to mention that the rights guaranteed by the shari'a came at a point when the abuse of the rights of women was the order of the day in most parts of the world. In fact, women were seen as chattel that can be used and disposed at will.⁵¹ To crown it all, the *jahiliyah* Arabs considered the birth of the girl child as a source of disgrace. The Qur'an responds to this practice as thus:

"And when one of them is informed of (the birth of) a female, his face becomes dark, and he suppresses grief. He hides himself from the people because of the ill of which he has been informed. Should he keep it in humiliation or bury it in the ground? Unquestionably, evil is what they decide."⁵²

Allah enjoins believers to appreciate his greatness in giving children to a person. He chooses the gender to give and in some occasions decide not to give children to a person. Allah speaks as thus:

"To Allah belongs the dominion of the heavens and the earth; He creates what He wills. He gives to whom He wills female [children], and He gives to whom He wills males. Or He makes them [both] males and females, and He renders whom He wills barren. Indeed, He is Knowing and Competent."⁵³

The abuse of the right of women was so extreme and unimaginable. This can be appreciated from the fact that they were so cruel against the girl child to the extent that they even bury her alive. The Qur'an states:

"And when the girl [who was] buried alive is asked. For what sin she was killed."⁵⁴

⁴⁹ The General Assembly of the United Nations adopted the Convention on 18th December, 1979 and came into force on 3rd September, 1981 see United Nations Treaty Collections, available at https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?src=TREATY&mtdsg_no=IV-8&chapter=4&lang=en viewed on 1st November, 2022.

⁵⁰ Ahmad al-Raysuny, et al, *Miithaaq al-Isratufii al-Islam*, (Amman: Jamiatu al-Afafa al-Khairiyyah, 2008), at 61.

⁵¹ Jamal A., *Badawi, Status of Women in Islam*, (USA: n.p., 1990), at 6.

⁵² Al-Qur'an, *al-Nakht*:56-57.

⁵³ Qur'an, *al-Shura*:49-50

⁵⁴ Qur'an, *al-Taqweer*:8-9.

In specific terms, several rights mentioned under CEDAW can equally be found under Islamic law. The Convention guarantees every woman the right to education and declares that women must not be discriminated against in matters of education. This position is in consonance with Islamic law. This is because under Islamic law, every woman has the right to education and any attempt to deny women the right to education is contrary to Islamic principles.

The fact that education is placed as a top priority in Islam can be appreciated from the fact that the first verse that was revealed to the Prophet (PBUH) instructed the Prophet (PBUH) to read. The Qur'an states "Recite in the name of your Lord who created –Created man from a clinging substance. Recite, and your Lord is the most Generous –Who taught by the pen – Taught man that which he knew not."⁵⁵ Imam Bagwi opined that the fact that the first revelation of the Qur'an instructs the Prophet (PBUH) to recite the Qur'an is an indication that education is a matter of serious concern under Islamic law.⁵⁶

In fact, the Qur'an has gone extra mile to mention that the knowledgeable are the true servants of Allah that worship and appreciate his oneness because they know that He is the Almighty. The Qur'an states:

"Allah witnesses that there is no deity except Him, and (so do) the angels and those of knowledge – [that He is] maintaining [creation] in justice. There is no deity except Him, the Exalted in Might, the Wise."⁵⁷

In yet another verse, Allah says:

"...those that fear Allah truly among his servants are the knowledgeable of them."⁵⁸

To make the fact that knowledge is unambiguously revered by Islam clearer; the Qur'an added that the knowledgeable and the ignorant can never be equal. The Qur'an states:

"Allah has raised the status of the believers and the knowledgeable to a higher degree..."⁵⁹

⁵⁵ Qur'an, *al-Alaq*:1-5

⁵⁶ Bagwi, Y., *Malim al-Tanzil*, vol. 8, (KSA: Dar At-tayyibibatulinnashriWal-Tanzil, 1997), at 474.

⁵⁷ Qur'an, *Ali-Imran*:18

⁵⁸ Qur'an, *Fatir*:28

⁵⁹ Qur'an, *al-Mujadilah*:11

Similarly, the noble Prophet (PBUH) has equally mentioned in several traditions that seeking for knowledge is obligatory and it earns the individual eternal respect in one of his narrations the Prophet (PBUH) mentioned that:

“Acquisition of knowledge is obligatory for every Muslim male and female.”⁶⁰

This tradition has specifically mentioned both males and females. That means every woman is obliged by shari’a to seek for knowledge and since it is obliged by Islam, no person will be allowed to deny a woman the right to seek for knowledge.⁶¹ In another hadith, the Prophet (PBUH) stated that whoever sets his foot on a track for the acquisition of knowledge, Allah will make the road to paradise easy for him.⁶² In yet another narration, the Prophet (PBUH) said that the angels lower their feather out of respect for the person that has gone out in search of knowledge.⁶³

Furthermore, the Prophet (PBUH) himself was reported to have taught Abdullahi Ibn Abbas some important aspects of the Islamic faith. He said “O young man, I shall teach you some words, be mindful of Allah and Allah will protect you. Be mindful of Allah and you will find him in front of you. If you ask, ask of Allah and if you seek for help, seek for help from Allah...”⁶⁴

The above discussions made it clear that as far as the right to education is concerned, Islamic law and CEDAW have similar approach which is to ensure that women get education and no discrimination is done to them in respect of this right.

Similarly, the Convention has stated that State Parties must ensure that adequate measures are taken towards ensuring that women are not trafficked.⁶⁵ This position is well received under Islamic law.

Firstly, the act of trafficking itself is a wrongful act under Islamic law. This is in view of the fact that it involves the illegal and forceful movement of the woman against her will or

⁶⁰IbnMajah, M., vol. 1, hadith, 337

⁶¹ If the woman is married, the husband is expected to teach her religious knowledge in person. If he cannot due to busy schedule or lack of knowledge on his own side, then he must bring someone to teach her or allow her to go and seek for the knowledge herself.

⁶²Abu Dawud Vol. 3, hadith 317 and Tirmithi, M., hadith 2785.

⁶³Abu-Dawudhadith 3634

⁶⁴Tirmithi, M., Vol. 4, hadith 2516.

⁶⁵ Article 6

through deception. This act is clearly a wrong against another person which the Qur'an categorically prohibits. Authorities from the Qur'an and traditions of the Prophet (PBUH) have clearly indicated that it is wrong for a person to harm another.

The Qur'an states: "Indeed, the wrongdoers will not succeed."⁶⁶

The Messenger of Allah equally mentioned: "Do not harm and do not be harmed."⁶⁷

Secondly, most of the trafficked women are forced into prostitution or other immoral activities. Since *zina* is the likely end result of trafficking, that alone has made it illegal under Islamic law. Under Islamic law, believers are expected to stay away from anything that will lead to *zina*. The Qur'an states:

*"And do not approach unlawful sexual intercourse. Indeed, it is ever an immorality and is evil as a way."*⁶⁸

In yet another verse, Allah states:

*"The fornicator does not marry except a [female] fornicator or polytheist, and none marries her except a fornicator or a polytheist, and that [i.e., marriage to such persons] has been made unlawful to the believers."*⁶⁹

In a narration, the Messenger of Allah (PBUH) was asked "what is the greatest sin", he replied 'associating partner with Allah', he was asked 'what next' he said 'killing your own son so that he does not eat with you (fear of poverty)', he was asked 'what next' he said 'fornicating with the wife of a neighbour'.⁷⁰

In yet another hadith,⁷¹ the Prophet (PBUH) was asked a question and Allah replied "And those who do not invoke with Allah another deity or kill the soul which Allah has forbidden [to be killed], except by right, and do not commit unlawful sexual intercourse. And whoever should do that will meet a penalty."⁷²

In respect to trafficking in women, there is no doubt that both regimes are in agreement to the effect that it is unlawful to traffic women.

⁶⁶ Qur'an, *al-An'am*:21, see also Qur'an, *al-An'am*:135, Yusuf:23 and *al-Qasas*:35.

⁶⁷ Bukhari and Muslim.

⁶⁸ Qur'an, *Isr'a*:32.

⁶⁹ Qur'an, *al-Nur*:6, see also Qur'an, *al-Nur*:2 which provided a punishment of 100 lashes for *zina*.

⁷⁰ Bukhari, Vol. 6 hadith 4477.

⁷¹ Bukhari, Vol. 2 hadith 6861.

⁷² Qur'an, *Fur'qan*:68.

Similarly, the Convention is against any state of affair that seeks to automatically change the nationality of a woman or render her stateless due to marriage.⁷³ This position is similar to the position of Islamic law. Under Islamic law, though originally the concept of nationality as obtainable today does not exist under Islamic law, contemporary realities has made it necessary for individuals to belong to a state.⁷⁴

Traditionally, all Muslims are expected to be under the *Dar al-Islam* (Islamic State) with a leader (*khalifah*) who is expected to rule and guide people with justice and fairness. The Qur'an states: "Indeed this, your religion, is one religion, and I am your Lord, so worship Me."⁷⁵

The Qur'an states further:

*"And indeed this, your religion, is one religion, and I am your Lord, so fear Me."*⁷⁶

The issue of changing the nationality of a woman apart, Islamic law considers women as independent entity hence even change of surname due to marriage is not allowed under Islamic law. The position of Islam is that marriage is a contract between a man and a woman to live as husband and wife and not a sell of the wife to the husband.⁷⁷

Under Islamic, the father's name shall always be used as the surname and marriage cannot change that position. The Qur'an states with regards to the use of father's name as surname thus:

*"Call them by [the names of] their fathers; it is more just in the sight of Allah. But if you do not know their fathers – then they are [still] your brothers in religion and those entrusted to you. And there is no blame upon you for that in which you have erred but [only for] what your hearts intended. And ever is Allah Forgiving and Merciful."*⁷⁸

⁷³ Article 9(1)

⁷⁴ Yusuf Qaradawy, Does Citizenship Have meaning in Islam, available at <http://politicalislam.org/Articles/PI%20518%20-%20The%20Dichotomy%20of%20Citizenship%20in%20Islam.pdf>. Viewed on 25 June, 2014.

⁷⁵ Qur'an, *Anbiyya*:92.

⁷⁶ Qur'an, *Mu'minun*:52.

⁷⁷ Muhammad Shaybany, *al-Mabsut li al-Shaybany*, vol. 4, (Karaatashy: Idarah al-Qur'an waUlum al-Islam, nd), at 101; Ahmad Sawy, *Bulgatu al-Saliki li Aqrab al-Masalik*, vol. 1, (Beirut: Dar Kutub al-Ilmiyyah, 1995), at 356; Ali Al-'Adawy, *Hashiyatu al-'Adawy*, vol. 2, (Beirut: Dar al-Fikr, 1990), 51; Muhammad al-Sharbiny, *IqnaulilSharbiny*, vol. 2, (Beirut: Dar al-Fikr, 1995), at 408; Majid, M.K., *Family Law in Islam*, (Malaysia: Malaysian law Journal, 1999), at 31.

⁷⁸ Qur'an, *Ahzab*:5.

Furthermore, in cases of pregnancy and lactation, CEDAW demand that women must be given adequate nutrition and care.⁷⁹ This position is in consonance with Islamic principle because Islam considers the issue of giving women care during pregnancy as a very important rule.⁸⁰ Providing good nutrition and care to women during pregnancy is part of care for the health of the women. The Prophet (PBUH) said:

“Second to faith, no one has ever been given a greater blessing than health.”⁸¹

Similarly, the Prophet (PBUH) explains the essential things in life in the following words: “Whoever of you gets up in the morning feeling physically healthy, enjoying security and having his food for the day is like one who has the world at his fingertips.”⁸²

The discussion has made it clear that CEDAW and Islamic law have much in common in terms of protection provided for women. Though they have areas of agreement, there are areas they differ as well.

Table 1: Areas in common between CEDAW and Islamic laws:

Islamic law and CEDAW Areas in Common	Right to life, Education, Prohibition of abuse, Prohibition of trafficking, Prohibition of forced marriage etc
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5.0 PROVISIONS OF CEDAW THAT CONTRADICTS PROVISIONS OF ISLAMIC LAW

The contradiction between the two regimes is informed by the fact that some of the provisions provided by CEDAW are too extreme to the extent that they contravene established principles of Islamic law.

⁷⁹ Article 12(2)

⁸⁰Arfat, S., “Islamic Perspective of Children’s Right: An Overview”, (2013), Vol. 2, No. 1, Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities, at 300.

⁸¹Tirmithi, M., Vol.5, hadith 3558.

⁸²IbnMajah, M., Vol. 2, hadith 4141.

An examination of the spirit of CEDAW reveals that it aims to put both men and women on the same footing in every respect.⁸³ Under Islamic law, though women are respected and given all rights just like men, in marital relationship, a husband is considered by the shari'a as the leader of the family.⁸⁴The Qur'an states:

"Men are in charge of women by [right of] what Allah has given one over the other and what they spend [for maintenance] from their wealth. So righteous women are devoutly obedient, guarding in [the husband's] absence what Allah would have them guard. But those [wives] from whom you fear arrogance – [first] advise them; [then if they persist], forsake them in bed; and [finally], strike them. But if they obey you [once more], seek no means against them. Indeed, Allah is ever exalted and Grand."⁸⁵

This verse has clearly shown that Allah has placed the leadership of the family in the hands of the man. This is however not to show that the man is any better or special but rather to indicate that in every relationship Islam expects leadership and where there is no such arrangement, the result will always be vague.⁸⁶Ibn Kathir opined that the Qur'an used the word *qawwamuna*, this indicates that the man has authority, leadership and say over the woman.⁸⁷

Similarly, CEDAW states that the interest of the child shall be of paramount consideration in all actions.⁸⁸ Under Islamic law, though children are cherished and seen as a source of pride and joy. Their interest must always be protected in accordance with Islamic principles. The fact that Islam cherishes children can be appreciated from the Qur'an and other Islamic authorities that urge believers to carter for children. The Qur'an states:

"Wealth and children are [but] adornment of the worldly life."⁸⁹

⁸³ See the Preamble and Article 1 of the Convention.

⁸⁴ Al-Raysuny, n. 48, at 27.

⁸⁵ Qur'an, *Nisa*:34.

⁸⁶ Abu Jafar al-Tabari, *Jamiu al-Bayan fiiTa'wil al-Qur'an*, vol. 7, (KSA: Muassisatu al-Risalah, 2000), 591.

⁸⁷ Ibn Kathir, *Tasfir Qur'anal Azim*, vol. 2, (KSA: darutayyibatulinashriwaltawzi, 1999), at 292;

⁸⁸ Article 5(b); see also Article 16(1)(d).

⁸⁹ Qur'an *al-Qahfi*:46.

The Prophet (PBUH) is known for his love for children, in a narration, he was reported to emancipate the slave woman that brought him the glad tiding of the birth of his son Ibrahim.⁹⁰

The protection that is supposed to be accorded to children is expected to extend to protecting him from anything that will lead him astray thereby becoming a dweller of the hell fire. The Qur'an states:

"O you who have believed, protect yourselves and your families from a Fire whose fuel is people and stones, over which are [appointed] angels, harsh and severe; they do not disobey Allah in what He commands them but do what they are commanded."⁹¹

Furthermore, the Convention has mentioned that betrothal and marriage of persons below the age of maturity shall be void.⁹² This position is contrary to Islamic principle.

Under Islamic law, no age limit is set for marriage and no marriage can be rendered void based on the simple fact that the parties to such marriage have not attained the age of maturity.⁹³ In fact, the marriage of a minor is lawful under Islamic law so long as no harm is done to the girl and all the requirements of the law are satisfied.⁹⁴ Some even advocate for early marriage.⁹⁵ The concept of maturity under Islamic law is different from the approach of CEDAW.

Generally, under Islamic law, there is no specific age fixed for maturity. The two primary sources of Islamic law (Qur'an and hadith) are silent on the specific age of maturity. However, the Qur'an has made reference to attainment of maturity in several verses without mentioning a specific age. The Qur'an states:

⁹⁰ Al-Bayhaqy, A., *Sunan Kubra*, (India: Majlis Daratu lMugharif, nd), hadith no. 13440.

⁹¹ Qur'an, *Tahrim*:6.

⁹² Article 16(2)

⁹³ Muhammad ibn Yusuf ibn Abu Qasim Abdary, *Al-TajiWa Al-Iklil li Mukhtasir Khalil* Vol. 3, (Beirut: Dar al-Fikr, 1968), at 401. See also Abu Hassan Ali ibnAbdulsalam Al-Taswily, *Al-Bahjatu fi SharhiTuhfah* Vol. 1, (Beirut: Dar al-Kutub al-Ilmiyyah, 1998), at 33.

⁹⁴ Doi, I.A., *Sharia the Islamic Law*, (London: Taha Publishers, 1984), at 142

⁹⁵ Al-Raysuny, n. 48, at 34.

“And when the children among you reach puberty, let them ask permission [at all times] as those before them have done. Thus does Allah make clear to you His verses; and Allah is Knowing and Wise.”⁹⁶

The Qur’an states further:

“O you who have believed, let those whom your right hands possess and those who have not [yet] reached puberty among you ask permission of you [before entering] at three times:...”⁹⁷

In yet another verse Allah states:

“O you who have believed, let those whom your right hands possess and those who have not [yet] reached puberty among you ask permission of you [before entering] at three times...”⁹⁸

The Qur’an states further that:

“And when the children among you reach puberty, let them ask permission [at all times] as those before them have done. Thus does Allah make clear to you His verses; and Allah is Knowing and Wise.”⁹⁹

A very clear message from all these verses is that adulthood is recognized by the shari’a as a stage in the life of a human being where responsibility is acquired and a person graduates from the age of childhood into adulthood.

Muslim scholars have given their opinion based on the verses of the Qur’an and traditions of the Prophet (PBUH) that maturity under Islamic law is generally not determined by age but rather by physical indications. For the male child, maturity is attained by wet dream, change in voice or through growth of pubic hair and for the female by menstrual circle. Some scholars are of the opinion that adulthood simple means the age of marriage.¹⁰⁰

The four major schools of Islamic jurisprudence have given several opinions on the actual age of maturity. According to the Shafii and Hanbali schools, in the absence of the physical

⁹⁶ Qur’an, *Nur*: 59

⁹⁷ Qur’an, *Nur*: 58

⁹⁸ Qur’an, *Nur*: 58

⁹⁹ Qur’an, *Nur*: 59

¹⁰⁰ Ambali, M. A., *The Practice of Muslim Family Law in Nigeria* 2nd ed., (Zaria: Tamaza Publishing Company Ltd, 2003), at 147.

signs, maturity is automatically presumed at the age of 15 for both sexes.¹⁰¹ However, the Hanafi School of jurisprudence maintained that maturity for males is on attaining 18 years and 17 years for girls.¹⁰² With respect to the Maliki School of jurisprudence, there are various views, some jurists opined 18 years, some 17, while other mentioned 16 years.¹⁰³ Similarly, another area of contradiction between CEDAW and Islamic law is in the area of right to guardianship of the child. According to CEDAW, both parents (father and mother) must have the same say in the maintenance and upbringing of their child. This position cannot be accommodated under Islamic law. Though the father is always encouraged to consult and seek the opinion of the mother in matters relating to their children's upbringing, the final say rests with the father because under the shari'a he is the guardian of his children.¹⁰⁴ In fact, even where the father is deceased, the guardianship does not shift to the mother but rather a testamentary guardian of the father then to the court.¹⁰⁵ With respect to seeking the opinion of the mother in the upbringing of children, this is a very important aspect of creating friendly atmosphere in the family. It gives the mother a sense of belonging and confidence that she is a stake holder in the family. Allowing the woman to play her part is important and is in accordance with the teaching of the Qur'an and practice of the Prophet (PBUH) which encourage consultation and respect for the opinion of others. "And those who have responded to their Lord and established prayer and whose affair is [determined by] consultation among themselves, and from what we have provided them, they spend."¹⁰⁶ This verse has clearly indicated that Islam encourages the believers to make consultation in their affairs and are discouraged from making hasty decision.¹⁰⁷ Certainly child upbringing and decisions on fundamental issues that could affect the future of a child deserve more attention and seriousness than most things people engage in nowadays.

¹⁰¹ Basil Mahmud Al-Hafi, *Fiqh al-Tufulah*, (Syria: Dar al-NawÉdir, 2008), at 423.

¹⁰² Jamhud, M.S., *Himayatu Huquq al-Tiflu*, (Iskandariyyah: DaruFikri al-Jami'l, 2010), at 24.

¹⁰³ Muhammad Ibn Muhammad IbnAbdulrahman, *MuwahibJalil Li SharhMukhtasar al-Khalil*, vol. 6, (Madinah: Dar al-Alim Al-Kutub, 2003), at 633; AbdulrahmanWahib al-Deen Al-Baghdady, *Irshad al-Salik*, (Beirut:Dar al-Firk, nd), at 163.

¹⁰⁴ Abdalati, H., *Islam in focus*, (Indiana: African Trust Publication, 1975), at 133

¹⁰⁵ Pazeeka, S., and Cheshti, A.A., *Custody and Guardianship of Children According to Muslim Jurisprudence in Pakistan*, (2012), Vol. 3, No. 2, Academic Research International, at 465.

¹⁰⁶ Qur'an, *al-Shura*:38.

¹⁰⁷ Bagwi, Y., vol. 11, n. 54, at 197.

It is therefore appropriate to state that the father needs to consult the mother on important things that affect their children more than any other thing. The children’s education, feeding and environment are good examples of issues that have far reaching consequences on the child’s future hence the need for the family to put heads together in order to arrive at a sound decision.¹⁰⁸

Table 2: Islamic Law and CEDAW Areas of Contradiction:

Islamic Law	CEDAW
Men are leaders in the House	Men and women are equal in the House
Child protection based on Islamic tenets	Interest of the child shall be of paramount consideration
Child marriage is allowed based on certain conditions	Child marriage is totally prohibited
Men are guardians	Both men and women are guardians

6.0 ANY MEANS OF RECONCILIATION BETWEEN CEDAW AND ISLAMIC LAW?

The earlier discussion has made clear the fact that Islamic law and the Convention on the Elimination of Discrimination against Woman are ad idem on the fight against injustice, oppression and discrimination against women. They however disagree in certain issues such as child marriage, guardianship and best interest principle.

However, a very challenging task at this stage is to attempt to see whether these conflicts can be reconciled. It is important to mention that the revelation of the Qur’an has ended over 1400 years back. This can be deduced from the Qur’anic verse which states that:

“...Today I have completed for you your religion....”¹⁰⁹

Zahily opined that this verse indicates that no more revelation will come to prohibit or make lawful any position already established. That means any position established by the Qur’an from that will remain up to the end of time.¹¹⁰ This position has shown that no attempt at reconciliation will be valid if it attempts to change the position of the Qur’an or hadith.

¹⁰⁸ See also Qur’an, *Ali-Imrana*:158.

¹⁰⁹ Qur’an, *Maidah*:3

¹¹⁰ Wahbatu Zuhaily, *Tafsir al-Munir fi Aqidahwa al-Shariahwa al-Munhaj*, vol. 6, (Damascus: Dar al-Fikr al-Muashir, 1418 AH), at 75.

Though Islam is rigid, it is equally described as elastic in accommodating certain contemporary issues.¹¹¹ Muslim jurists are permitted to use their reasoning in arriving at decisions on contemporary issues not directly covered by the Qur'an, hadith or *ijma* (consensus opinion of Muslim jurists) but such opinion must be in accordance with the Qur'an and sunnah.¹¹² The authority for the legality of this position is derived from the Qur'anic verse which says:

*"Think deeply, O! you who have reasoning."*¹¹³

Since the Qur'an and sunnah cannot be changed, the best way of reconciling the conflict is to amend CEDAW to be consistent with the Islamic position without defeating the spirit and intent of the Convention. For example, with respect to the position that the husband and wife are equal, an addition could be made to indicate save as provided under Islamic law.

Similarly, with respect to declaring a marriage void due to immaturity, the best way to reconcile this conflict is to add 'save marriage contracted according to Islamic law.' If this excluding clause are put in place, it will save the situation and the position of the Convention will not affect marriage conducted in accordance with Muslim law.

Furthermore, the conflict relating to guardianship of children is not too clear compared to the ones discussed earlier. This is because the Convention did not expressly mention the word guardianship. Since the Convention expects equality of powers on matters relating to the child's upbringing, that by extension means the power over guardianship. To reconcile this conflict, the Article shall be amended to indicate that the provision of this article is not intended to deny the power of a father over the guardianship of his children.

A very important addition that is necessary to avoid conflict between the Convention and Islamic is to categorically mention in the Preamble to the Convention that any provision of the Convention that is in conflict with Islamic law will not apply to any person that profess the religion of Islam.

¹¹¹Ekin, E.E., *The Sources and Schools of Islamic jurisprudence*, (2012), vol. 3(3), Am. J. Soc. Mgmt. Sci., at 108.

¹¹² Ibid

¹¹³ Qur'an, *al-Hashr*:2

7.0 CONCLUSION

CEDAW and Islamic law aim is to ensure that women interest is protected. The areas of agreement between these two regimes by far outweighs their areas of differences. It is therefore important to state that bridging these gaps will help in giving women more protection as Muslims will readily accept the Convention. Since Islamic law is not a man-made law and as its message has been completed with no means of changing it, CEDAW should be amended to agree with the principles of Islamic law or at least mention that its areas of conflict with Islamic law ill not apply on Muslims. If that is done, most Muslim nations that have reservations on some of the provisions of the Convention will withdraw such reservations which will greatly enhance better protection for women.